

Balaam Inscription from Tell Deir 'Allā

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The Tell Deir 'Allā inscription, also known as the Balaam inscription, describes a series of ink on plaster fragments which survive from the site Deir 'Allā in the Valley of Succoth in ancient Gilead (modern Jordan). The plaster text was originally displayed on the inner walls of a building that was subsequently destroyed by an earthquake. Discovered by H. Franken in 1967 and later published by J. Hoftijzer and G. van der Kooij in 1976, scholars piece together the fragments into two combinations (see esp. the editio princeps by Hoftijzer and van der Kooij 1976 as well as Caquot and Lemaire 1977; Hackett 1980). The text was originally dated to the Persian period (Franken 1967), but the date was quickly refined on paleographic grounds to the mid-8th century or earlier (already Naveh 1967; Cross 1969). While the script can be classified as Aramaic, the dialect has been much disputed in previous scholarship. The options include Aramaic (Hoftijzer and van der Kooij 1976), Canaanite (Hackett 1980; 1984; Rendsburg 1992; Pat-El and Wilson-Wright 2015), a local dialect (McCarter 1991), or a separate branch of Northwest Semitic (Huehnergard 1991). Regardless of its technical linguistic classification, some scholars employ the term "Gileadite" on the basis of its distinct local character (Kaufman 1988; Greenfield 1991; Rendsburg 1992). Since its discovery, the Deir 'Allā inscription has piqued scholarly interest because the inscription mentions a certain "Balaam son of Beor" (בלעם בר בער) who appears also in the biblical book of Numbers and subsequent biblical and Jewish tradition. According to Num 22-24, Balaam (called בִּלְעָם בֶּן-בְּעוֹר 'Bil'ām son of Bē'ōr') was a non-Israelite diviner from Pethor who was hired by the Moabite king Balaq son of Šippor to curse Israel but instead blesses them in four separate discourses (מְשָׁל) according to the word of the Lord. The Deir 'Allā inscription confirms the biblical tradition that Balaam was a diviner as it calls him "a seer of the gods" (חֹזֵה אֱלֹהִים) and recounts a nocturnal theophany which he received "according to the utterance of El" (כַּמְשָׁא אֵל). However, although it contains parallels with the biblical traditions about Balaam, the Deir 'Allā text is not itself an extrabiblical portrayal of the biblical narrative. Combination I describes the report of Balaam's nocturnal vision which he received from the gods (אֱלֹהִים) at the behest of El (אֵל), a Semitic word meaning "god" but also a well-known deity in the ancient Near East, especially among Levantine religions such as in ancient Israel, Phoenicia, and Ugarit. Distracted from the contents of the theophany (lines 1-4), Balaam fasts and weeps, then recounts the vision to his companions. He tells them about the "council" (מוֹעֵד) of the "Shaddai-gods" (שִׁדְיָיִם = šaddāyīn), a word undoubtedly related to the Hebrew theonym El-Shaddai (אֱלֹהֵי שִׁדְיָיִם). Although its etymology is debated, the negative portrayal of the Shaddai-gods in the Deir 'Allā inscription suggests the possibility of associating it with a Northwest Semitic word for "demons" (Heb. שִׁדְיָיִם, Aram. שִׁדְיָיִם; cf. Akk. šēdu) and/or a verb meaning "to destroy" (√šdd). Another widely accepted alternative for El-Shaddai, however, is to understand the element šad(d)ay as meaning "mountain, wilderness," thus rendering "God of the Mountain/Wilderness" (Delitzsch 1896; Albright 1968; Cross 1973; Knauf 1999). Regardless of the correct etymology, the biblical tradition (Num. 24:4, 16) situates Shaddai (often translated as "the Almighty") as the source of Balaam's theophany rather than its subject matter. In the Deir 'Allā inscription, the Shaddai-gods have commissioned a deity called Šagar-wa-lštar to sew up and block out the heavens (line 6) which in turn creates darkness and chaos on earth. Interpretations of the second half of the first combination diverge significantly, but according to one interpretation, incantations were used to ward off the impending doom and thus the land is saved (Levine, COS 2.27). The contents of Combination II and its relationship to the first combination are much less certain given its highly fragmentary state, but it seems to have something to do with El's construction of a necropolis and/or the netherworld, called the "house of eternity" (בֵּית עֹלָמִין). Moreover, Balaam's name does not appear in Combination II. In conclusion, the Deir

'Allā inscription is ultimately our best example of a (semi-)mythological text from the Iron Age Transjordan. While scholars continue to debate aspects of its linguistic classification and interpretation, there can be no doubt that it serves as an important source for reconstructing the history of religion in the ancient Levant.

Date Range: 850 BCE - 750 BCE

Region: Tell Deir 'Alla

Region tags: Southern Levant, Jordan, Jordan Valley, Levant

Location of a modest settlement mound called Tell Deir 'Alla, located in the Central Jordan Valley. It is situated in one of the most fertile areas of the Jordan Valley, also known as the Zerqa Triangle, near the Zerqa River (biblical Jabbok). The mound finds itself along several important ancient trade routes, running both north-south and east-west.

Status of Readership:

- ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Hendricus Jacobus Franken. 1967. "Texts from the Persian Period from Tell Deir 'Allā." *Vetus Testamentum* 17 (4): 480–81.
- Source 2: J. Hoftijzer and G. van der Kooij. 1976. *Aramaic Texts from Deir `Alla*. *Documenta et Monumenta Orientis Antiqui* 19. Leiden: Brill.
- Source 3: Jo Ann Hackett. 1980. *The Balaam Text from Deir `Allā*.

Notes: Other bibliography mentioned throughout encyclopedia entry. For an introduction and English translation of the Balaam inscription from Tell Deir 'Allā, see Baruch A. Levine, "The Deir 'Alla Plaster Inscriptions (2.27)" in *The Context of Scripture*, vol. 2, *Monumental Inscriptions from the Biblical World* (ed. William W. Hallo and K. Lawson Younger, Jr.; Leiden/Boston: Brill, 2003).

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.thetorah.com/article/balaam-the-seer-from-the-bible-to-the-deir-alla-inscription>
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.biblicalarchaeology.org/daily/ancient-cultures/ancient-israel/balaam-son-of-beor-part-three/>

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Notes: The text was composed with a combination of red and black ink, a practice known from elsewhere such as ancient Egypt. The body of the inscription was written in black ink while the red ink was used for the outline and some of the words (perhaps for emphasis, but the precise function remains unknown).

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Clay

↳ Clay object

– Other [specify]: Plaster

Notes: Inscription is ink on plaster as it once hung on the inner wall of an ancient building before the building's destruction by earthquake.

↳ Type of clay

– Type of clay: Plaster

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: Plaster was used as an ancient building technique. The ink text was written on the inner wall of the building or possibly on a stela that was suspended from a wall.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: It seems possible that the ink on plaster text was placed on a stela or similar object before suspending on the wall of the building.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb

– No

- ↳ Cemetery
 - No
- ↳ Temple
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Shrine
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: Possibly a shrine or sanctuary.
- ↳ Altar
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Devotional marker
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Cenotaph
 - No
- ↳ Church
 - No
- ↳ Mosque
 - No
- ↳ Synagogue
 - No
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
 - No
- ↳ Monument
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
 - Field doesn't know

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– Field doesn't know

↳ Library/archive

– Field doesn't know

↳ Specify

– Specify: The precise function of the building is unknown, although has been described alternatively as a sanctuary or a manufacturing/distribution center where religious activity may have taken place.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Field doesn't know

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Deir 'Allā inscription represents a unique Northwest Semitic dialect somewhere in between Aramaic or Canaanite, but its classification remains unclear. It's possible that the language of the text represents a distinct literary (possibly religious/sacred) language, or more likely just the local dialect of the region.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Field doesn't know

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

↳ Is it hidden?

– No

↳ Can it be touched?

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Does the text serve a protective function?
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: The possible mention of incantations in the text perhaps suggests an apotropaic function of the text itself, but this is highly conjectural. The reading of an "incantations" in the text is dubious.

- ↳ Does the text serve a healing function?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: The possible mention of incantations in the text perhaps suggests an apotropaic function of the text itself, but this is highly conjectural. The reading of an "incantations" in the text is dubious.

- ↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?
 - No

- ↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?
 - No

- ↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

– Field doesn't know

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Field doesn't know

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Field doesn't know

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The fact that the Balaam traditions exist independently in Deir 'Allā as well as in the Hebrew Bible and post-biblical Judeo-Christian traditions suggest some degree of importance to the oral/literary tradition associated with him.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Blood or Marriage relations

Notes: Balaam is always referred to as the "son of Beor" in the Deir 'Allā inscription and Hebrew Bible alike. In the Hebrew Bible, he is also described as stemming from a geographical location called "Pethor".

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Although the text describes multiple deities, it seems possible that the god El functions as the supreme

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although the text describes multiple deities, it seems possible that the god El functions as the supreme high-god in this text.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural beings can reward
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Supernatural beings can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Some scholars interpret Combination II line 6 as a reference to El's "lovmaking" (also known from Ugarit, e.g. KTU 1.23).

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This seems likely.

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?
– Yes

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?
– Field doesn't know

Are other categories of beings present?
– Other [specify]: N/A

Does the text guide divination practices?
– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?
– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?
– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?
– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?
– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?
– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?
– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Notes: While the text itself does not require fasting, Balaam is mentioned as fasting and weeping as the result of his dream theophany.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Field doesn't know

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A tribe

Notes: The people of the region of Gilead in the Transjordan seem to be organized as an agropastoralist tribe.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: N/A

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: N/A

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Field doesn't know

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Balaam Inscription from Tell Deir 'Allā, Hackett, Jo Ann. *The Balaam Text from Deir 'allā*, 1980.

Reference: Balaam Inscription from Tell Deir 'Allā, Hoftijzer, J., and G. van der Kooij. *Aramaic Texts from Deir `alla*, 1976.

Reference: Balaam Inscription from Tell Deir 'Allā, Hackett, Jo Anne. "The Dialect of the Plaster Text from Tell Deir 'alla". *Orientalia* 1984, no. 53/1 (1984): 57-65.

Reference: Balaam Inscription from Tell Deir 'Allā, Rendsburg, Gary. *The Dialect of the Deir 'alla Inscription*, 1992.

Reference: Balaam Inscription from Tell Deir 'Allā, Pat-El, Na'ama, and Aren Wilson-Wright. "Deir 'allā as a Canaanite Dialect: A Vindication of Hackett". *Epigraphy, Philology, and the Hebrew Bible: Methodological Perspectives on Philological and Comparative Study of the Hebrew Bible in Honor of Jo Ann Hackett*, 2015.

Reference: Balaam Inscription from Tell Deir 'Allā, Donner, Hebert, and Wolfgang Röllig. *Kanaanäische Und Aramäische Inschriften*, 2002.

Reference: Balaam Inscription from Tell Deir 'Allā, Levine, Baruch A.. "The Deir 'alla Plaster Inscriptions (2.27)". In *The Context of Scripture, Vol. 2: Monumental Inscriptions from the Biblical World*, 2003.